

EXPRESSION OF INTELLECT IN SPEECH ACTIVITY

¹Akhmedova Muyassar Khadimatovna, ²Zhorakulova Dildora Ziyadullaevna

¹Doctor of psychology

¹Department of General Psychology acting professor

²Psychologist. Ph.D., acting associate professor

²Tashkent State Pedagogical University

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Abstract. *Speech is a tool of thought. The article analyzes speech and its role in human activity. The direct dependence of speech on the activity of the mind, as well as thinking, is expressed. It also expresses the uniqueness of human speech, the intelligence of the state of mind, the originality of erudition. The speaker's intelligence in most cases is determined by his lexical richness and logic.*

Keywords: *language, intelligence, linguistics, speech, society, thinking, communication, vocabulary.*

Introduction. Today, as a result of the development of human consciousness and the development of society, people in all aspects of our lives use speech to exchange ideas, express their mental states, and solve other problems. Speech and thinking are human characteristics. It is impossible to imagine human development without them.

Speech is a multifaceted process of the development of connections between people arising from the needs of joint activity. Speech (relationship) involves the exchange of information between participants. This takes into account the communicative aspect of the relationship. People turn to language first when entering into a relationship. Another aspect of speech is the mutual action of the participants in the relationship - in the process of speech, they exchange not only words, but also actions.

It should be noted that speech is not only a means of communication between people, but also a necessary means of thinking, a tool for thinking. We make all sorts of judgments through words, that is, with the medium of language. In this case, of course, our comments will be in accordance with the grammar rules of the language.

Main part. Language and speech are dialectically related socio-historical, socio-psychological phenomena, language exists as a tool of communication, and speech as a method of communication [6.13]. Speech is the process of using the unique socio-individual weapon called language, the manifestation of language units and possibilities in a necessary and permanent relationship with the objective existence, thinking and situation. Speech is a formal language. In a broad sense, it consists of words, phrases and sentences.

The role of speech is also very large in volitional actions. We stop ourselves from some bad behavior through speech. In addition, through language, we plan our actions, that is, we subordinate all our actions to some set goal. All this will be done through language.

Speech embodies the individual characteristics of a person. Each person's speech is unique. Through a person's speech, it is possible to determine his thinking, vocabulary, interests, character traits, illnesses, emotional state, mood, etc.

Language and personality traits are interrelated and individual. How a person laughs depends in many ways on how he addresses himself to the interlocutor or the audience. Regardless of where a person's speech is, whether it is a pulpit, a meeting, or a desk, he should know how to fully express his personal qualities. For this reason, it is necessary to know that the characteristic of a person's reception is from his speaking behavior. Knowing this information is useful and

necessary. We often imagine that our mental states, intellect, and eruditions are received by our signal listeners without seeing it.

Erudition is mainly evaluated by the logic, richness, appropriateness of the speech. It is known to everyone that when a person expresses his opinion on a given question, he can quickly find arguments in an unexpected (spontaneous) situation to confirm his point of view, he is an erudite person. However, although a person has a lot of words, their meaning is very shallow or there is almost no (worthwhile) logic. Erudition is having deep and extensive knowledge and is associated with vocabulary. It is known that not all erudites can be brilliant speakers. There are also those who are very poor in speech and weak in the art of speech.

The speaker's intelligence is evaluated by the lexical richness and logic of the spoken words. The development of the intellect, the variety in the free choice of words, the ease of creation, and various irregularities in the vocabulary in many cases lead to violations.

Speech also informs the audience about the speaker's state of mind. Therefore, it often awakens vital observation in people. When people are tense under the pressure of their psyche, they have difficulty expressing their thoughts in words and sentences in their speech. There are several factors that indicate this, including:

a) the amount and length of pauses (stopping) increases compared to speech in a normal state. These pauses represent instability. When observed from the outside, it seems that the speaker does not know what to say. Usually, such cases are more common in the speech of paralinguists (bilinguals). To repeat without thinking in the middle of a sentence or to find a word, "here is this", "this", "in general" are used. In the middle of the speech or to complete the process of pause (stop), words like "have you seen", "you know", "here", "again" are used.

b) in the case of repetition or pressure, the variety of words and vocabulary decreases. In such cases, the vocabulary of speech is poor; the speaker is mainly connected with the lexical units that he uses in his daily life and tries to express his thoughts with the participation of these words. Some of them tend to repeat the thought at such a time. All this adapts the audience to receive the speaker without enthusiasm.

c) speech under pressure is also characterized by grammatical incompleteness. "Well, what kind of instruction is this?", "Hmm, in general...", "As you know...", "this problem is not one of the last" [9.56].

In many cases, there are long sentences consisting of three parts. These can be difficult to understand the first time you take them. Usually the speaker finishes the sentence with difficulty at such a time. In such cases, the listener stops following the sequence of the speech, and often does not even reach it. Speech is the main tool that measures the human psyche. On the basis of the speech, the listeners conclude the disorder or normality of the psyche. It will be difficult to distinguish the pathology clearly. Sometimes the shortcomings can be improved. Some defects can be distinguished only by experts. Symptoms of the disease characteristic for psychiatrists include: Logorrhoea - non-stop talking. He moves on to another subject without finishing the listener's question, or answer, or objection. The story speaks, introduces new characters and makes others speak. They say that such people do not stop talking. Speech persuasion is the repetition of an idea or a single uncomplicated idea in the human mind as a result of the influence of arousal.

The speaker cannot move on to another topic, he repeats his thoughts in part or in whole. Speech discontinuity or incoherence - speech may be grammatically correct but not understandable. Such speech has no meaning. The stickiness of speech is the expression of uncomplicated events with too much deliberation and detail, it is called slurredness of speech. Advocacy and rationality are baseless and fruitless considerations. Irrational nonsense.

The presence of these and various other unusual characteristics about the speaker will be unattractive to the mass audience and undermine the potential of the speaker. Many people have a hard time coming to a decision. But in the process of listening to a defective speech, they perceive a feeling of unpleasantness towards the speaker.

The cases listed above are clear pathologies or disorders. These are almost subtle aspects of the speaking person. If the created words did not obey the models of language, they would not "fit" within the framework of speech thinking and human behavior in language, they would not be filtered and stored in the vocabulary of thousands of people. A language preserves only the means that conform to the laws tested by the generations of its speakers. The least compared to organisms have important linguistic abilities: these words are distinguished not only by reproduction, but also by real word-building creativity. Their authors are people who know the language and its norms perfectly, who intuitively possess it as a factor of self-awareness[2.1212].

The role of internal speech in the intellectual activity of a person is important. Inner speech, according to L. S. Vygotsky, is "a completely separate, independent and unique function of speech, a special internal plan of speech thinking that mediates the dynamic relationship between thought and word." A word belongs to both speech and thought, and in its simplest form it is a living cell containing the main features characteristic of speech thought in general. From a psychological point of view, the meaning of a word is, first of all, a generalization of the signified. But generalization, L.S. Vygotsky explains, is an "extraordinary act of verbal thinking" that perceives reality in a completely different way than what is reflected in direct feelings and perceptions. At the same time, the word is also a means of communication, so it is a part of speech. The word is meaningless and no longer applies to thought or speech. But when a word acquires meaning, it immediately becomes an organic part of both (thought and speech) [5.307].

Gradually, with the formation of internal speech, attention from the "outside", social mediation becomes internal. The formation of the "mental movement" that leads to the formation of an idea simultaneously leads to the formation of attention directed to the imagined content. In the future, speech seems to "disappear", but with subjective difficulties in concentration, a person emphasizes the object or content of his interest with the help of internal speech and tries to suppress interfering stimuli. Conclusion and recommendation [1.54].

Summary. A specific form of text formed by a speaker or a writer is an expression, which is not only a linguistic phenomenon, but also a phenomenon of spirituality and sophistication.

Correctness of speech is its most important communicative quality. Because if the speech is not correct, its other communicative qualities, i.e. logicity, accuracy, appropriateness of the purpose, will also be damaged.

So, speech activity can change based on external influences and examples. In this case, a person can correct the shortcomings of his speech, re-educate him, and realize his personal potential. Because speech is a powerful weapon for a person, mastering it carefully prepares the ground for the future, leads to perfection. Speech culture is an attitude towards the use of language, a tool of communication and intervention. The higher the level of attitude of language representatives to the possibilities of this unique weapon, other factors in its use: thinking, consciousness, existence, various situations and circumstances, the higher the level of speech culture.

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